

Research Paper

Sustainable Reforms and Performance Measurement in Nigeria: An Appraisal of 2023 Fuel Subsidy Removal

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ABSTRACT:The first fiscal reform embarked on by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu on assumption of office in 2023, was the fuel subsidy removal. The rationale behind this bold action was for the purpose of curbing corruption, reduction of fiscal leakages, re-channel resources for rebuilding critical infrastructural facilities and increase social investment. The reform triggered significant socio-political debates due to its immediate and medium term impact on socio-economic well-being of many. Including the research 'Sustainable Reforms and Performance Measurement in Nigeria: An Appraisal of 2023 Fuel Subsidy Removal'. The paper examined the extent to which intended objectives were achieved. Backed by Public Choice and Public Value Theoretical underpinning. It adopted secondary textual materials, systematically organised and reviewed thematic and content analysis, this enabled identification of patterns. Through the lense of performance measurement impact indicators, effectiveness, efficiency, equity, responsiveness, transparency, accountability and sustainability, fuel subsidy removal impact was evaluated. Findings show that so far, the reform failed to deliver equitable benefits to citizens. Inflationary pressures disproportionately affected vulnerable groups, and palliative measures were poorly managed, and non-sustainable. Furthermore, low level transparency mechanisms weakened public trust in the ability of government to manage and re-invest freed-up funds derived from reform process. The study concluded that while Nigerian leadership demonstrated strong political will in curtailing subsidy expenditure, medium or long term measures requires more balancing between economic rationality and social justice. The paper recommends that government should strengthen social protection systems, institutionalize transparency in usage of subsidy savings. Refocus towards sustainable investment in healthcare, education, and infrastructural development.

Keywords: Fuel Subsidy; Fuel Subsidy Removal, Performance Measurement, Public Policy, Public Policy Reform.

I. Introduction

For more than four decades, the Nigerian government took the responsibility of subsidizing Premium Motor Spirit (PMS), popularly referred to as petrol, to stabilize domestic prices and protect citizens from fluctuations in international oil markets (Onyishi and Ogbu, 2024). As well as make it affordable for the citizens. Although this intervention aimed to mitigate economic hardship, various assessments indicated that fuel subsidy evolved into a structurally problematic and financially unsustainable public expenditure that fostered rent-seeking behavior exacerbating inefficient resource allocation, and systemic corruption within the downstream petroleum sector (BudgIT, 2022; Transparency International, 2023). By 2022, the subsidy regime reportedly consumed approximately ₦4 trillion, exceeding annual budgetary allocations for health, education, and infrastructure combined (NEITI, 2023; IMF, 2023). Historically fuel subsidy had been accused to be a drain in the Nigerian economy, its removal can be traced to several factors. Attempts by various administrations to stabilise the economy by withdrawal of payments met with stiff resistance. In 2012, when former President Goodluck Jonathan withdrew subsidies paid for petroleum products so that resources could be freed up for other developmental purposes, the government experienced resistance. Actual subsidy payment continued under opaque arrangements labelled as 'under recovery'(BudgIT, 2022).

In May, 2023, during the inaugural speech, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu, in his statement, announced that 'Fuel Subsidy is Gone'. Explaining that the policy was positioned as a fiscal rescue strategy with objectives to;

- i. Fiscal sustainability: Reducing excessive government spending on subsidies.
- ii. Reallocation of resources: Channel savings into infrastructural and social services
- iii. Ensuring efficiency in promoting private sector participation in domestic refining and downstream market,
- iv. Curb corruption, by eliminating rent-seeking and smuggling associated with subsidy.
- v. Price liberalisation. Allow fuel price to reflect market realities.

Framed as an economic imperative designed to reduce fiscal leakages, attract private investments, channel resources into productive sectors such as welfare, infrastructure, and human capital development (Federal Ministry of Finance, 2023). The world global financial institution's assessment of fiscal and developmental challenges in Nigeria, advised the removal of subsidy, floating of currency, that is devaluation and increase taxation. Its reaction after the removal of fuel subsidy was that this reform represents "one of the most significant public policy transformations in recent history" (World Bank, 2023). The advice to rebase the economy may sound good but it comes with challenges. Nigeria with her large population, prior to the removal was the fourth largest economy in Africa, but fell back to the fifth position thereafter. Yet government defended the policy of fuel subsidy removal as a pathway to fiscal stability. Public policies serve as strategic governmental instruments for addressing socio-economic challenges, enhancing national stability, and improving the general welfare of citizens through deliberate intervention mechanisms(Olaopa, 2022). Also "the issue of over-reliance on oil as the primary source of revenue, coupled with inadequate diversification efforts, has left the economy susceptible to external shocks"(Amadi and Ogidi, 2024), leaving behind deprivation, hunger, poverty and high inflation. Within public administration discourse, the success or failures of policies affecting the welfare of citizens, can easily be assessed through adoption of performance indicators such as; effectiveness, efficiency, equity, responsiveness, transparency, and sustainability (Adejumo and Igbokwe-Ibeto, 2023). While hoping that the federal government and its agencies will effectively and efficiently implement the policy, considering cost-benefit implications.

This policy was expected to release funds for other critical sectors like health care, schools, power generation and empowerment projects. Emphasizing the fact that transparency and accountable mechanisms will be put in place for utilizing the savings from subsidy removal. As well as equitably distributing the burden of subsidy removal among different groups in Nigeria, while reducing the burden on the vulnerable groups, by cushioning its effects on poor and low income earners, through various

mechanisms and economic interventions. Although widely supported by international financial institutions, the policy triggered an immediate increase in the pump price of petroleum products by over 230%, with ripple effects across the economy (NBS, 2023). Prices has been fluctuating between 2023 to early part of 2025, independent petroleum marketers had sold their products based on the market forces of demand and supply. End users bought the products at a pump price of between N850 and N1300, depending on ones location, as there was price differences between urban and rural areas. A development that led to increased costs of transportation, higher food prices, and worsened household poverty levels (Adeniran and Olofin, 2023; National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). However, in reality the reverse has been the case, empirical evidence shows that the aftermath of the subsidy removal triggered severe inflationary shocks. Citizens sees the reform as imposing disproportionate burdens on the poor and vulnerable. This policy shift has therefore raised critical administrative and governance questions. If we may ask, is there sustainability implications of the policy for Nigeria's economic future? How responsive has the government been to public reactions and economic shocks resulting from subsidy removal? Lack of transparent communication on subsidy savings raised public suspicion of mismanagement(CDS, 2024). Citizens increasingly demand that public resources are used in ways that improve their welfare and ensure that development results are measurable and visible (World Bank, 2023). This makes performance measurement essential in assessing sensitive policies such as the 2023 fuel subsidy removal, where outcomes directly affect citizen welfare.

Meanwhile, the debate of scholars has been whether removal has effectively achieved declared objectives such as enhanced efficiency and fiscal accountability (Ezeani and Ugwu, 2024). Concerns persist on whether this reform has promoted social equity, protected vulnerable groups, and demonstrated responsiveness to citizen expectations amid heightened socio-economic hardship (Oseni, Bello, and Yusuf, 2024). Transparency with respect to revenue savings and reinvestment strategies has also become central issue of analysis(Centre for Social Justice, 2023). Questions regarding long-term sustainability and developmental outcome remains unresolved, necessitating empirical evaluation. So, evaluating subsidy removal through established performance indicators strengthens "evidence-based assessments of public policies providing insights into operational strength, implementation deficit, and necessary corrective mechanisms"(Ochei and Adebayo, 2023). Nigeria has historically struggled with policy performance due to weak political will, poor monitoring systems, corruption, and limited institutional capacity (Okeke, 2022; Omotola, 2023). These persistent structural weaknesses equates performance evaluation as critical for understanding whether the 2023 fuel subsidy removal, despite its economic rationale, has delivered promised benefits to Nigerians or not. The aim of this study is to evaluate the reform involving the 2023 fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria, using key performance indicators in public administration.

II. Research Questions

This study is guided by the following questions:

- i. What is the impact of 2023 fuel subsidy removal on the socio-economic well-being of vulnerable groups in the society?
- ii. How responsive has the government been to public reactions to economic shocks resulting from fuel subsidy removal?

Theoretical Perspectives

Public Choice theory is linked to Buchanan and Tullock(1962), The theory applies economic reasoning to political behaviour. In the book, "The Calculus of Consent", they posit that various category of citizens act based on self-interest. The theory states that often, the preferences of organized interests groups shape policy outcome. It predicts that reforms threatening powerful interests groups are likely to be stalled, watered down, or reversed. This played out after the subsidy removal reforms of 2012, 2016, it also affected the case of 2023. There were resistance from petroleum products marketers, labour unions and political actors benefiting from the status quo. Those at the corridors of power maintain subsidies as a populist tool to secure electoral support, while marketers exploited weak oversight to claim fraudulent subsidy payments (Akinola, 2018). Public Choice theory offers a better understanding of the reasons behind resistance and non-sustainability of fuel subsidy removal. Public Value Theory, is another

paradigm proposed by Moore, (1995 ; 2023). The framework reveal some indices of economic reforms that incorporate social legitimacy, public communication, and citizen welfare. The theory argues that public administration should create value not just in economic terms, but in fairness, trust and legitimacy. According to Moore, (2023), government success must reflect outcomes that citizens value, including fairness, legitimacy, and trust. Rapid inflation and transportation hardship after subsidy removal have strained public trust, raising questions about legitimacy (Nwosu and Ezenwa, 2024). Evaluating fuel subsidy removal policy from this lens would involve ascertaining whether it enhanced or diminished public trust and inclusiveness. These theories provide complementary perspectives and help situate the evaluation of Nigeria's 2023 fuel subsidy removal policy within global discourses on governance and accountability.

III. Conceptual Review

Fuel subsidy

Subsidy is a governmental policy to bear some financial burden for a particular programme or project, product or services, in order to reduce the price and cost of production and selling prices to the end users. Fuel subsidy is a policy adopted by the Nigerian government to absorb part of the cost of production, therefore reducing or minimising the market price sold to consumers. Discontinuance of this support from government, which is known as subsidy removal means that fuel prices has to be determined by market forces. Hence the astronomical rise in pump price of petroleum products, triggering rises in costs of transportation, prices of foods in the open markets, and other social services.

Historical Context of Fuel Subsidy Removal in Nigeria

The global oil shocks in the mid-1970s and Nigeria's transition to a major petroleum-exporting economy, gave impetus to the emergence of Fuel subsidy in the country. The government introduced subsidies to ensure that citizens benefited directly from the nation's oil wealth by stabilizing domestic pump prices and preventing the pass-through of global crude price volatility (Fagbemi and Osakwe, 2021). According to the former Finance Minister, "For three decades, Nigeria had subsidized the price of gasoline at the pump to make it cheaper for its population. The world thirteenth largest oil producer at the time had limited refining capacity, so crude oil was exported, and refined petroleum products were imported and sold to the public at below market prices. The government covered those subsidies, paying them to the marketers and importers who brought in the products"(Okonjo-Iweala, 2018). Over time, however, subsidy payments escalated significantly. Confirming this, Okonjo-Iweala, (2018), attest that "subsidies were a heavy fiscal burden, but all attempts to phase them out over the years were strongly resisted by labour union, civil society, and the general public.

Several attempts have been made to reform or remove the subsidy, starting with the Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida's administration. In 1986, the then Nigerian Head of State, General Ibrahim Babangida tried partial subsidy removal as part of market liberalization reforms under Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP), but the move was met with intense public resistance (Olawale and Adebisi, 2019). In 2004, during the Olusegun Obasanjo's administration the fuel subsidy was completely phased out, attracting protest from labour unions, but was soon restored in 2006, costing the federal government about \$2 billion. The restoration was due to the rise in oil prices. Then Umaru Yar'Adua's government in 2009 abolished subsidy on kerosene. Okonjo-Iweala, (2018, pp.28-34), explains that by 2011, the burden of the subsidies was absurdly heavy on the nation's finances. Net Federation Revenues totaled about N52 trillion, and subsidy payments had ballooned to N1.73 trillion(\$11.2 billion), or 33 percent of net revenues". Explaining how by mid-August 2011, almost "N1.3 trillion (\$8.4 billion at the prevailing exchange rates) had already been paid to over 143 beneficiaries companies. By the end of 2011, a total of N1.73 trillion (\$11.2 billion) would come due as subsidy payments on imported oil. Of which kerosene subsidies were N310.4 billion (\$2 billion). This represented 2.7 percent of GDP, 33 percent of net Federation Revenues, and 38 percent of the federal government's budget. With the phase-down, consumers went from paying N65 at the pump for a liter of gasoline to N97(\$0.62 or equivalent of \$2.36 a gallon)". It was confirmed that "kerosene subsidy clearly did not benefit majority of poor people targeted. Whereas kerosene was supposed to retail at N50per liter (with a subsidy of N100 per litre paid by government), a survey

conducted by the Finance Ministry in 2012 showed that retail prices across the country ranged from N97 to N200 per litre. Budgeting for a non-existent subsidy therefore constituted in our minds a source of revenue leakage"(Okonjo-Iweala, 2018). Following the massive fraud on oil subsidy regime, even the governor's forum were in support of its phaseout. The then Finance Minister, went further to express her fears "at the nation's finances, I knew that Nigeria could not sustain such a punishing fiscal regime of oil subsidies". After engaging a wide team of experts and interests groups in discussing about the benefits and drawbacks of the eventual removal of fuel subsidy, they came to the conclusion that; "Although the subsidy benefited the poor people by lowering transportation and other costs, it benefited the rich far more, and (2) there would be better ways to target low-income people directly with benefits, using the resources that would accrue from phasing out the subsidy" (Okonjo-Iweala, 2018). Also, on January 1, 2012, President Goodluck Jonathan announced full subsidy removal, arguing that it fuelled economic leakage and corruption; however, the policy triggered #Occupy Nigeria movement, a nationwide protests and a swift partial reinstatement of subsidy (Olawuyi, 2020). The protesters demanded the resignation of the President or he should be impeached. The persistence of subsidy was largely due to its political sensitivity, as Nigerians viewed it as one of the few tangible benefits of oil economy. However, government bearing the humongous cost of fuel subsidy, rather than reduce the financial burdens of the poor, the benefits was disproportionately on wealthy and middle class urban dwellers, while fostering corruption in fuel importation and distribution(Okonjo-Iweala, 2012).

The aftermath of negotiation between President Jonathan's government and representatives of labour unions led to a compromise, "government pulled back from a total phaseout to a 50 percent phaseout of the subsidies on refined petroleum and gasoline. Labor and civil society demanded and government agreed that the money saved would be applied to expenditures in transportation, maternal and child health, and employment creation, which would benefit poor people, and to infrastructure and other investments that would benefit society at large. The monies would be managed transparently"(Okonjo-Iweala, 2018). Thus giving birth to Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Program (SURE-P). The House of Representative Ad-Hoc Committee to Verify and Determine the Actual Subsidy Requirements under Resolution No.HR.1/2012 confirmed in its reports that the the government's "inability to continue to pump endless amounts of money into the seemingly bottomless pit that was referred to as the petroleum products subsidy. It explained that the annual subsidy payment was huge, endless and unsustainable". The Report confirmed that there were fraudulent payments, "that the subsidy regime as operated between the periods under review (2009-2011) was fraught with endemic corruption and entrenched inefficiency. Much of the amount claimed to have been paid as subsidy was actually not for consumed PMS [petrol]. Government officials made nonsense of the PSF (Petroleum Subsidy Fund. One of the recommendation of the Ad-Hoc Committee was the repayment of N1.067 trillion (\$6.8 billion) deemed to have been misappropriated as subsidy payments during the period under review, by the NNPC and others"(Okonjo-Iweala, 2018). The report showed some levels of mismanagement of funds from the oil subsidy regime.

Then, in 2016, Mohamadu Buhari administration announced "a shifting toward deregulation, the fiscal loss did not abate. Despite government's efforts to close the loopholes, a covert subsidy regime persisted, due to exchange rate distortions and political insensitivity" (Eze and Ugwuanyi, 2021). By 2022, subsidy costs had risen to ₦4.39 trillion, surpassing expenditure on health and education combined and contributing significantly to Nigeria's borrowing crisis (NNPC, 2022; IMF, 2023). Thus, when President Bola Ahmed Tinubu announced full subsidy removal on May 29, 2023, the Nigerian Petroleum Company Limited adjusted the pump price of petrol from an average of N185 per litre to between N488 to N550 nationwide. The prices of other essential goods and services sky rocketed, following a spiralling effects from the increase in the pump price of petroleum. Triggering socio-economic consequences, with Nigerians experiencing sharp increases in living costs. The inflation rate rose from 22.4% in May 2023, to over 25% by August 2023(NBS, 2023), it then went rocket high thereafter. From 2024, to the beginning of 2025, the prices of petrol went between N1000 to N1300 per litre. Hence, the historical trajectory reflects a persistent struggle to balance economic rationality with social equity and political legitimacy. Public resistance to subsidy removal has historically been driven by perceptions that cheap fuel is one of the few direct benefits citizens receive from the oil economy (Ibietan and Ogu, 2023), as much as personal interests. However, research indicates that the wealthiest 20% of Nigerians captured most subsidy benefits, while poor households experienced limited direct advantages (World Bank, 2022; Ajao and Aluko, 2023).

Furthermore, the subsidy system became a major source of rent-seeking and corruption estimated to have cost Nigeria over \$10 billion in leakage between 2006 and 2015 (NEITI, 2020). Consequently, scholars widely argue that the subsidy regime became economically unsustainable, fiscally inefficient, and socially inequitable (Akinyemi, Oni, and Ojo, 2022; Onyekpere, 2023). This historical backdrop shaped the rationale for Nigeria's 2023 full subsidy removal, which focused at redirecting government expenditure towards sectors that are productive, and of utmost importance to most citizens. Sectors like education, healthcare, infrastructural development. In comparative analysis with previous subsidy attempts, unlike the 2012 attempt under Goodluck Jonathan, the 2023 removal was not reversed despite protests. This suggests stronger political will. However, similar to 2012, the lack of trust and inadequate social protection measures persist as a major challenge. Compared with past reforms, the current policy appears more fiscally decisive but equally vulnerable to social unrest.

Performance Measurement of Subsidy Removal

Performance measurement has become a cornerstone of global public sector activity, helping governments (organisations) monitor and improve the implementation of public policies (Hatry, 2006; Talbot, 2021). It involves a systematic evaluation of inputs, outputs, outcomes, and the ultimate impacts of public programmes on society. Thus, it reflects a shift from the traditional bureaucratic orientation which emphasized rule-compliance, to a result-oriented and citizen-centered administrative culture (Behn, 2003; Osborne, 2020). According to Armstrong (2018), performance measurement in government should not only track outputs such as the number of beneficiaries, but also outcomes such as; poverty reduction, empowerment and citizens's satisfaction. Performance measurement therefore reduces wastage, increase trust in government, and promotes evidence-based policymaking (Adewumi and Okoye, 2023). Within the Nigerian context, performance evaluation helps with the uncovering of implementation failures that have historically undermined well-designed reforms due to corruption, weak oversight, and political interference (Olaopa, 2018; Nwosu and Ezenwa, 2024). In contemporary public governance, emphasis is placed not only on efficiency in resource utilization but also on delivering broader democratic values such as strengthening accountability, promoting transparency, equity, responsiveness, and sustainability (Moynihan, 2008). The United Nations Development Programmes also emphasizes principles of equity, accountability, transparency, and responsiveness in assessing governance quality (UNDP, 2023).

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Evaluating Fuel Subsidy Reform

The complexity of public governance requires adopting key Performance Indicators, these are multidimensional, to capture not only economic results but also social and political implications (IMF, 2023; Adebajo, 2023). KPIs measurement tools used to assess whether policies achieve intended goals (Poister, 2010; Kusek and Rist, 2018). This study adopts six widely recognized KPIs to evaluate the 2023 fuel subsidy removal, these are: i. Effectiveness, ii. Efficiency; iii. Equity; iv. Responsiveness; v. Transparency and Accountability; vi. Sustainability. These KPIs form the basis for evaluating the strengths, weaknesses, and administrative implications of the policy. Although data from government sources may introduce political bias, and also information from private sources like advocacy groups can as well expose the findings to advocacy bias (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019). Due to its time frame, since the reform is still unfolding, the work is unable to measure long-term outcomes (ADB, 2023).

Empirical Studies on Subsidy Removal in Nigeria

Institutions and scholars have examined the implications of subsidy removal. Adenikinju, (2013) found that subsidy removal could improve efficiency and attract private investment in the downstream oil sector, but warned of inflationary effects. Meanwhile, Sambo, (2017) explained that subsidy removal without social protection mechanisms disproportionately harms the poor, reducing equity in policy outcomes. The World Bank (2021), at the end of their study, recommended subsidy removal as a pathway to fiscal stability, but emphasized the need for compensatory programmes to mitigate social costs, knowing that on the long run, the outcome of subsidy removal will affect the vulnerable groups. BudgIT (2022), reported that subsidy payments in 2022 surpassed Nigeria's capital budget, reinforcing arguments for its removal. The International Monetary Fund (2022), assertions that subsidy removal could free up to 3% of GDP annually for developmental expenditure if supported by transparent reforms in the petroleum sector,

is a pointer to the need for transparency. So in 2023, they came up with a report that any reform must be accompanied by targeted social protection (World Bank, 2023). In addition to the fact that scholars have emphasized the importance of timely social protection measures and accountability to maintain reform legitimacy (Adebajo, 2023). These scholars added that poor communication strategy reduced reform legitimacy, since there was no prior consultation with the people or their representative before the announcement was made. "Inadequate citizen engagement, and weak enforcement or performance tracking" (Nwoko and Ibrahim, 2023). CDS (2024) reports worsening poverty following the 2023 withdrawal. NBS (2024) shows inflation reached record highs, intensifying food and transport crisis. Evaluations of past reforms reveal poor accountability in government expenditure, Isa et al (2024) found that post-removal outcomes depend significantly on governance quality, particularly proper management of anticipated fiscal savings. For Nwosu and Ezenwa (2024), weak transparency undermines public trust in subsidy savings. IMF (2023, 2024), asserts that reforms must strengthen governance and improve transparency. There are empirical consensus amongst scholars in the findings, noting that fuel subsidy removal improves fiscal health, but implementation quality determines social outcomes.

Although a substantial body of knowledge exists on the complexities of fuel subsidy reforms in Nigeria, several research gaps persist. Few researchers employ multi-criteria KPI frameworks integrating governance and welfare lenses, and due to the recency of the 2023 reform, much research have not been done in this area. Therefore, the paper contributes by offering a comprehensive KPI-based evaluation of Nigeria's 2023 subsidy removal, incorporating dimensions often overlooked in existing literature.

IV. Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative descriptive research design widely used in policy evaluation, because it makes for a deeper understanding of social, institutional, and administrative dynamics that cannot be fully captured through number alone (Silverman, 2020; Mohajan, 2022). Descriptive design systematically examines phenomena by describing their characteristics, pattern, and implications (Creswell and Creswell, 2021). This design is considered appropriate because performance evaluation involves multi-dimensional constructs such as effectiveness, efficiency, equity, transparency, and responsiveness, which rely heavily on interpretive and contextual analysis rather than statistical testing (Bryman, 2020; Ojo and Afolabi, 2023). Evaluating the 2023 fuel subsidy removal requires qualitative insights from policy documents, expert opinion, and socio-economic reports, making this approach suitable for capturing both intended and unintended consequences of the reform. This study relies solely on secondary data, which is widely recognized as a valid approach in public administration research due to accessibility of government records, institutional reports, and scholarly literature (Saunders et al., 2019). The paper relied on documentary review technique, which involves systematic retrieval, categorization, and content analysis of publicly available materials (Bowen, 2020). Priority was placed on, i. Official government sources (to ascertain policy intent and fiscal outcomes). ii. Independent reports (to capture public sentiment and socioeconomic effects).

Policy Analysis and Performance Evaluation

What has been the impact of 2023 fuel subsidy removal on the socio-economic well-being of vulnerable groups in the society? An overview of the May 29, 2023 Fuel Subsidy Removal Policy, during the inaugural speech, of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu, marking a decisive break from decades of subsidy regimes that consumed trillions of naira annually. The government justified the policy on the grounds that subsidy payments had become fiscally unsustainable, they argued that subsidy removal would free resources for social investments, reduce corruption in the oil importation sector, and stimulate private investment in domestic refining (World Bank, 2023). However, the immediate aftermath was characterized by sharp increases in transportation costs, food inflation, price inflation, and general hardship among citizens. Economists argued that the system adopted in handling the removal of fuel subsidy, largely benefitted fuel smugglers and wealthier urban vehicle owners rather than the poorest citizens (Okonjo-Iweala, 2012; Onyekwena and Akanonu, 2023). How responsive has the government been to public reactions and economic shocks resulting from subsidy removal? Implementation of the promised palliative measures, was slow and inconsistent, raising concerns about equity and responsiveness (SERAP,

2023), on the part of government. The analysis is consistent with studies indicating that energy price shocks intensify food insecurity and poverty in import-dependent economies (Ogunleye & Adekoya, 2024)

V. Results and Discussions

This research evaluated the 2023 policy on Fuel Subsidy Removal in Nigeria using performance measurement indicators. These indicators are commonly applied in public administration studies. The following key findings emerged:

i. Effectiveness: Measures the extent to which policy goals are met. In subsidy removal, this concedes into developmental gains (Akinyemi and Ogunode, 2023). The policy achieved fiscal savings by eliminating subsidy payments, freeing up trillions of naira for potential investment in social sectors. However, tangible benefits of these savings have not been sufficiently felt by citizens due to delays and inconsistencies in reallocating funds. Meaning that the policy was effective in fiscal savings but less effective in reallocation of resources.

ii. Efficiency: While fiscal resources were preserved, the economic costs to citizens were immense. Inflationary pressure, rising transportation costs, and eroded household incomes reduced the overall efficiency of the policy. Palliative measures were poorly implemented, undermines cost-effectiveness. In other word, efficiency was undermined by high inflation and poor palliative management.

iii. Equity and Inclusiveness: This aspect of performance indicators examines whether policy benefits or burdens were fairly distributed, "particularly among low-income households who spend a higher share on transport and energy" (Sambo, 2017; CDS, 2024). The burden of subsidy removal fell disproportionately on low-income and vulnerable groups, worsening inequality. Limited coverage of social safety nets meant that equity was the weakest area of policy performance. That is, the issue of equity was not adequately handled, poor citizens bore disproportionate burdens of the after effects of fuel subsidy removal. The policy has widened inequality, making equity the weakest performance dimension.

iv. Responsiveness: This indicator on responsiveness, considers governments speed and capacity in addressing citizen concerns, including the issue of palliative distribution. Official responses to citizen concerns were largely reactive, rather than being proactive. Public outcry was met with promises of palliatives and wage awards, but these were slow to materialize. Scholars argues that lack of prior consultation and communication contributed to citizen mistrust (Ibrahim and Bakare, 2024). Lack of preparation to handle any eventuality created a sense of governmental betrayal of citizens trust, and moreover, the fact that the process of fuel subsidy removal was an imposition on the citizens, resulted to citizens mistrust of the good intentions of the leadership, Reports on public outcry has it that civil resistance and labor unrest followed subsidy removal (NLC and TUC Reports, 2023). Government responses have been reactive rather than pro-active, preventive or people-centred.

v. Transparency and Accountability: The decision to terminate fuel subsidy regime with no clear framework for tracking how subsidy savings would be utilized, labeled the reform as lacking transparency. The UNDP (2023) emphasizes equity, accountability, transparency, and responsiveness in assessing governance quality. Transparency and accountability mechanisms in handling the excess surplus recovered from the withdrawal of subsidy reform remain insufficient. Civil society groups have raised concerns about insufficient accountability mechanisms, echoing Nigeria's historical misuse of subsidy-related funds. On policy transparency, Omotola, (2024), confirm that sudden implementation without a clear rollout plan limited accountability. On the need to manage the savings, Civil society demands auditing and publication of funds' utilization (BudgIT, 2023). Accountability Gaps: Studies note persistent corruption risks in subsidy savings management(Ojo and Adeyemi, 2024). Weak transparency continues to threaten policy legitimacy and public confidence

vi. Sustainability: This is of various types, starting with, political sustainability, policy reversal risks remain high if citizen welfare concerns remain unaddressed(Abe and Anigbogu, 2024). Though the policy has potential for long-term sustainability if properly managed, particularly in terms of redirecting funds to infrastructure and stimulating domestic refining capacity. Apart from the Dangote Refinery that is

functioning now, though privately owned and managed, the rest four refineries owned and managed by the federal government of Nigeria, are under utilised, underfunded and moribund. For economic sustainability, according to experts, long-term gains depend on controlling inflation and strengthening fiscal discipline (IMF, 2023; Osaghae, 2024). Based on this findings, irrespective of the fact that sustainability potential exists, yet sustainability can be threatened by inflationary trends, public distrust, and lack of proper reinvestment of funds, due to weak governance structures. The policy has potential but hinges on improved governance and public trust.

V. Conclusion

The analysis of the 2023 fuel subsidy removal policy in Nigeria focused on the period beginning May 2023 to the present, with emphasis on the policy's economic, social, and political implications. Apart from the fact that the process of fuel subsidy removal was an imposition on citizens, long-term impacts may not be fully measurable yet, as official data on savings and reinvestment of funds may be subject to political bias or lack of transparency. Despite these constraints, the paper delved into timely and rigorous evaluation of one of the country's most significant public policy. The removal of fuel subsidy in 2023 represents a significant economic reforms in Nigeria's recent history. From a public administration standpoint, the policy created a situation of 'push and pull' between fiscal rationality and social equity. On one hand, it succeeded in eliminating a costly and corruption-prone subsidy regime, signaling strong political will. On the other hand, the policy imposed disproportionate hardship on citizens, particularly the poor, without adequate compensation. Showing that though it intends to align with the principles of efficiency and long-term sustainability, but it falls short on equity, responsiveness, and transparency.

Any economic reform must incorporate social legitimacy, public communication, and citizen welfare. The Nigerian government never communicated the policy to the citizens before the president announced fuel subsidy removal in 2023. Although such reform mechanism demand real improvement in government communication strategies, to build trust and manage expectations. Open and unfettered communication often leads to enhanced responsiveness, giving rooms to citizens engagement in public decision making process. The paper concluded that a truly successful policy must balance economic logic with social justice and legitimacy in governance. As such, demands robust governance reforms, transparency in management of accrued funds meant for savings, and stronger citizen-focused interventions to achieve its intended goals. The 2023 fuel subsidy removal policy remains a work in progress, the removal though economically necessary, cannot be evaluated solely on fiscal grounds.

VI. Recommendations

Based on the findings, the paper recommends that;

- 1.** Government should strengthen social protection systems, introduce targeted cash transfers, food security interventions, and subsidized transportation for vulnerable groups to cushion effects of hardship. Expand coverage of wage support and provide incentives for small businesses.
- 2.** Government should direct subsidy savings into visible and high-impact projects, refocus its resources in the area of equitable and sustainable social investment, in healthcare, education, power supply, and infrastructural development, particularly in sub-urban and rural areas. Ensuring that these projects are equitably distributed across states and socio-economic groups.
- 3.** Government should create a publicly accessible Subsidy Savings Accountability Portal so that funds from subsidy removal will be saved and adequately accounted for. Also institutionalize transparency in its usage, including the allocation formula.
- 4.** Independent auditors should be part of oversight mechanisms, to institutionalize transparency in the usage of subsidy windfalls.
- 5.** Participatory consultative mechanisms should be established between, labor unions, civil society and the authorities, before major economic reforms are embarked upon, accompanied by strong compensatory

mechanisms, to ensure policy sustainability. Strengthen regulatory frameworks to ensure that market liberalization does not translate into consumer exploitation.

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